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RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PHOTOVOLTAICS MARKET IN THE WORLD AND IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article analyzes the photovoltaic market in Ukraine and in the world. It determines the place of photovoltaics among renewable energy sources. Also it reviews the origin of solar energy in the countries of the world and presents the leading countries in the generation of solar energy. In the article is determined Ukraine's place in the European and global solar energy market.

Keywords: renewable energy, photovoltaic, solar energy, solar energy market.

Introduction. Energy is the backbone of the global economy. However, while a few decades ago it was based primarily on fossil resources, in recent years the influence of alternative energy sources has been growing. This is due to both the exhaustibility of fossil resources and their negative impact on the environmental situation on the planet.

Solar energy is the second largest source of renewable energy in the world, second only to hydropower. Thanks to the installation of new photovoltaic installations in previous years, global solar capacity in 2020 exceeded that of wind power.

Analysis of recent research and publications. They presented an analysis from 2015 to 2021 on the share of renewable energy in general and solar energy in particular in global electricity generation, the weighted average cost of solar energy (LCOE) compared to other sources, and proposed scenarios for the medium-term development of solar energy in 2022-2026 [1].

Regarding the prospects for the development of solar energy in Ukraine, it is worth noting the study "Solar energy in Ukraine: analysis and its role in ensuring economic security" [2]. The authors consider that the development of the alternative energy sector is a long-term energy and environmental priority for Ukraine, as provided by domestic legislation and participation in international agreements.

Y. Dziadykevych, M. Buriak and I. Liubezna [3] studied aspects of solar energy development in Ukraine in order to increase the economy of fossil energy sources and energy security of the country.

However, the results of research on the photovoltaic market, covered in these works, do not take into account new trends in the basic indicators of the energy sector due to the constant change in the global economy in the scale and structure of light energy consumption.

Purpose of work. The purpose of our research is to conduct a retrospective analysis of solar energy use in Ukraine and the world. The article focuses on the study of basic indicators characterizing the situation and trends in the development of solar energy.

Analysis and discussion. Solar energy is the second largest source of renewable energy in the world, second only to hydropower. Thanks to the installation of new photovoltaic installations in previous years, global solar capacity in 2020 exceeded that of wind power.

According to the report of the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), at the end of 2021, 3,064 GW of renewable generation capacity was earned worldwide, including 40% from hydroelectric power plants (1,230 GW), 28% from solar power plants and 27% from wind power plants (Figure 1). According to statistics, solar energy and wind have grown many times faster than hydropower over the years [4].

Figure 1. Structure of installed RES capacities in 2021, GW.

Source: estimated by the authors to [4]

Solar and wind have nearly equal market shares with 849 GW (843 GW of photovoltaic and slightly more than 6 GW of solar thermal generation) and 825 GW, respectively. Other renewable energy sources (with a combined share of about 5%) include 143 GW of bioenergy, 16 GW of geothermal and 524 MW of marine energy [4].

In 2022, the global consumption of solar energy reached 12.41 EJ, which is 3448.3 TW-hours (Appendix A). In this period, solar energy volumes grew by 27.63% year on year, adding 2.69 EJ, i.e. about 747.2 TWh of generating capacity. The growth in this type of energy exceeds the growth in all renewable sources (1.49%), such as wind, geothermal, bioenergy and bio-fuel production. At the same time, the increase in all capacities from renewable sources, fossil fuels, nuclear energy and hydroelectric power is 5.52% [5].

According to British Petroleum [5] (Appendix A), the annual increase in global consumption of solar electricity since 2001 is more than 20%. Moreover, the average growth rate of renewable energy was 15%, and the annual growth in the volume of all total energy resources did not exceed 5% and fluctuated on average within 1-2%. The annual growth rate of solar energy storage capacity makes solar energy the fastest growing renewable energy source.

Since solar energy in the last decade has been not only the largest sector of the world's electric power industry in terms of annually commissioned capacities, but also attracted investments, this gives reason to assert that humanity is confidently moving into the sunny future of clean renewable energy.

Mankind has always tried to use the potential of the Sun, but it was only 69 years ago, in 1954, that they began to turn sunlight into electric current (Table 1).

Table 1

Discoveries that marked the beginning of solar energy

Year	Person/company	Content	Importance
1883	Charles Fritts, American inventor	He first used selenium to turn light into electricity.	The efficiency of this method was very low, but it laid the foundation for solar energy.
1921	Albert Einstein	He explained the phenomenon of the photoelectric effect - the release of electrons under the influence of light and received the Nobel Prize for this.	This discovery became the cornerstone for solar energy.
1946	American engineer Russell Ohl	He patented the silicon solar cell	Silicon is still used in the manufacture of solar panels.
1954	researchers of the American company Bell Labs	They designed a silicon solar cell capable of achieving 6% energy conversion efficiency under direct sunlight.	Thanks to this discovery, the company released the world's first photo-modules.
1985	scientists from the Australian University of New South Wales	They invented a way to increase the efficiency of solar panels up to 20%	Thanks to this, solar power plants have become cheaper, and the capacity of solar energy generation has increased.

Source: completed by the authors to [6].

Although the mass production of solar panels began in 1963 [6], however, the mass construction of solar power plants began somewhat later (table 2).

Table 2

The origin of solar energy in the countries of the world

Year	Countries	Year	Countries	Year	Countries
1983	USA	1998	Argentina	2009	Bulgaria, Croatia, Estonia, Ireland, Israel
1984	United Kingdom	2000	Colombia, Trinidad & Tobago, Egypt South Africa, Western Africa	2010	Venezuela, North Macedonia, Slovakia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Algeria, China Hong Kong SAR, Vietnam
1989	Italy, Portugal, Spain	2001	Eastern Africa, Middle Africa	2011	Ukraine, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland
1990	Finland, Germany, Mexico, Switzerland, China, Japan, South Korea	2002	Morocco, Bangladesh	2012	Kazakhstan, Malaysia, Brazil, Chile
1991	Australia	2004	Belgium, Greece, Cyprus, Czech Republic	2013	Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kuwait, Oman
1992	France, Canada, Netherlands	2005	Philippines	2016	Uzbekistan
1993	Austria, Sweden	2006	Iran, Thailand	2017	Colombia
1995	India	2007	New Zealand, Pakistan		
1996	Denmark	2008	Hungary, Slovenia, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Singapore		

Source: completed by the authors to [5].

The first country in the world (according to British Petroleum) to use solar energy was the United States of America. In 1983, only 3 GWh of electricity was generated. From 1984 to 1991, nine power plants with parabolic trough concentrators were built in California with a total capacity of 354 MW [7, p. 6]. By the end of 1991, US solar power plants had already generated 0.5 TWh of electricity. As of 1991, only 13 countries out of 92 operated solar power plants, namely 7 countries in Europe, 4 countries in Asia and 2 countries in North America (USA and Mexico).

In 1992, the United Nations adopted the first global climate agreement, the Framework Convention on Climate Change [8]. It was then that the call to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and switch to renewable energy sources (RES) was first heard at a high level.

This prompted other countries to install solar power plants. In the 1990s, this process began in European countries, and since the 2000s, Asian and African countries have joined them. Most countries in the Middle East have joined since the 2010s.

In 2015, the Paris Agreement was adopted [9], which provided for concrete steps by the governments

of all countries to curb global warming. Since burning fossil fuels emits more greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, governments and businesses must invest in the development of clean energy technologies to prevent a climate crisis.

The last countries to introduce solar energy in 2016-2017 were Uzbekistan and Colombia.

Note that by the end of 2022, among the countries of the world, only Iceland does not use solar energy to generate electricity and heat. However, despite the low level of insolation in Iceland, electricity in this country is 100% generated from renewable sources. 13 % of Iceland electricity comes from geothermal power, 87 % of the clean energy comes from hydropower. Iceland's glaciers and mountains are perfect for hydroelectric generation [10].

For many years (until 2001), the United States played a leading role in the development of global solar energy (table 3). However, if in 1989 the country accounted for almost 97% of the total volume of this energy, then in 2000 it was only 45%. Such dynamics is associated with an increase in the global production of solar electricity by other countries [5].

Table 3

Share of leading countries in solar energy			
Year	TOP-5 Countries	Volume, Terawatt-hours	Share, %
1989	USA	0.300	96.77
	Spain	0.006	1.94
	Italy	0.002	0.65
	Portugal	0.001	0.32
2002	Japan	0.700	38.89
	USA	0.600	33.33
	Germany	0.200	11.11
	Australia	0.100	5.56
	China	0.048	2.67
2006	Germany	2.300	39.66
	Japan	2.000	34.48
	USA	0.800	13.79
	China	0.100	1.72
	Australia	0.100	1.72
2015	China	39.500	15.51
	USA	39.400	15.47
	Germany	37.200	14.61
	Japan	34.500	13.55
	Italy	22.900	8.99
2021	China	327.000	31.67
	USA	165.400	16.02
	Japan	86.300	8.36
	India	68.300	6.62
	Germany	49.00	4.75
2022	China	427.700	32.34
	USA	206.200	15.59
	Japan	102.400	7.74
	India	95.200	7.20
	Germany	60.800	4.60

Source: estimated by the authors to [5].

Since 2002, Japan has become the world leader in the development of solar energy. Given the island nature of the country and the exhaustive hydropower resources, Japan has focused on solar energy and since 2002 has occupied about 40% of this market. The world leaders in the use of solar energy in 2002 were the USA, Germany, Australia and China. The TOP-5 countries in 2002 generated more than 90% of the world's solar energy.

In 2006, Germany increased the generation volumes. To support renewable energy, Germany has introduced a number of regulations, in particular the Renewable Energy Act [11]. According to this law, it is possible to enter into long-term contracts (even up to 20 years) with green energy suppliers.

In total, Germany, Japan, America, China and Australia in 2005 provided more than 90% of the total capacity of the world's solar energy. Moreover, the first two countries accounted for 75% [5].

Since 2015 and to this day, China has been the world leader in the development of solar energy. It should be noted that the TOP-1 in the photovoltaic market by this country was achieved due to the annual increase in the production of solar electricity at a level of at least 200%. A sharp increase in the generation of solar energy in China began in 2013 due to the reduction in the cost of its production.

According to Solar Power Europe [12] and British Petroleum [5], the world leaders in the use of solar energy in 2021-2022 were the China, USA, Japan, India and Germany. The TOP-5 countries in 2021-2022 generated about 70% of the world volumes, and China and America accounted for almost half of the world market for this energy.

It should be noted that the solar market in India is quite promising. Huge solar power plants have been installed in the country – in the deserts of Rajasthan and Gujarat. Many of these are public-private partnerships run by utility companies – they send electricity to the grid. As for private companies, the government subsidizes the investment of Indian companies in this area and eliminates the payment for the transmission of renewable energy [13]. The world's largest solar power plant (2,245 GW) was built in 2019 at Bhadla Phalodi tehsil, Jodhpur district, Rajasthan, India [14].

As for Ukraine, solar energy is a relatively new industry, but with a rapid pace of development. It should be noted that the entire territory of Ukraine is suitable for the development of electricity and heat supply systems using solar energy. However, the most promising regions of the country are the Crimean Peninsula and steppe Ukraine. It should be added that in Ukraine the annual solar radiation is comparable to countries that actively use solar collectors (e.g. Sweden, Germany, USA).

According to British Petroleum, in Ukraine electricity from solar radiation (0.03 TWh) was for the first time generated in 2011 (table 4).

Table 4

Ukraine on the global solar energy market

Year	Renewables: Generation - Solar Total World, Terawatt-hours	Growth rate compared to the previous period, %	Ukraine		
			Renewables: Generation-Solar, Terawatt-hours	Share, %	
				value	place
2011	65.60	–	0.03	0.05	34/80
2012	101.50	154.73	0.30	0.30	27/85
2013	138.60	136.55	0.60	0.43	20/89
2014	196.40	141.70	0.40	0.20	30/89
2015	254.70	129.68	0.50	0.20	31/89
2016	327.58	128.61	0.49	0.15	37/90
2017	445.47	135.99	0.72	0.16	38/91
2018	576.23	129.35	1.11	0.19	35/91
2019	703.95	122.16	2.93	0.42	29/91
2020	846.23	120.21	5.37	0.63	21/91
2021	1032.50	122.01	6.33	0.61	21/91
2022	1322.6	128.1	5.1	0.38	25/91

Source: estimated by the authors to [43].

Over the next 10 years, Ukrainian solar power plants increased generation to 6.33 TWh of electricity in 2021, however, the share of Ukrainian solar energy did not exceed 0.61% of global generation volumes in 2021.

In 2022, there was a reduction in solar energy generation, as some of the SPPs were damaged due to hostilities or were located in the occupied territory.

The first step to encourage the production of solar (as well as other renewable) electricity in Ukraine was the introduction of annually renewable "green tariffs". This tariff was adopted at the end of 2008. According to it, electricity obtained from alternative sources is purchased by the state at tariffs that are an order of magnitude higher than the market value. The program of „green tariffs” is designed until 2030 with a gradual reduction in the cost of 1 kW of electricity so that at the end of the program its cost is compared with the standard.

For example, for solar power plants located on the roofs of buildings, in 2010 the „green tariff” was (excluding VAT):

- 484.05 kopecks per 1 kW/h for a station with a capacity of up to 100 kW;
- 463.00 kopecks per 1 kWh for a station with a capacity of more than 100 KW [15].

For photovoltaic facilities located in open areas, the highest tariff was set at 505.09 kopecks per 1 kWh (excluding VAT). Consequently, in 2010, ground-based solar power facilities in Ukraine could receive a "green tariff" at the level of UAH 5.06. for 1 kW (with VAT) or about 60 euro cents for 1 kW/hour. Moreover, the market is considered "interesting" if the tariff is over 28 euro cents [15].

Let us determine the place of Ukraine in the European solar energy market (Table 5).

Table 5

Ukraine on the European solar energy market

Year	Renewables: Generation - Solar Total World, Terawatt-hours	Growth rate compared to the previous period, %	Ukraine				
			Renewables: Generation-Solar, Terawatt-hours	Share, %		Growth rate compared to the previous period, %	
				value	place	value	place
2011	47.11	–	0.03	0.06	16/47	–	–
2012	72.23	153.34	0.30	0.42	13/47	1000.00	3/47
2013	86.55	119.81	0.60	0.69	12/47	200.00	12/47
2014	97.34	112.47	0.40	0.41	17/47	66.67	47/47
2015	108.23	111.19	0.50	0.46	17/47	125.00	21/47
2016	112.40	103.85	0.49	0.44	19/47	98.00	23/47
2017	122.76	109.21	0.72	0.59	17/47	146.94	9/47
2018	136.17	110.92	1.11	0.82	16/47	154.17	10/47
2019	150.44	110.48	2.93	1.95	10/47	263.96	1/47
2020	175.65	116.76	5.37	3.06	8/47	183.28	2/47
2021	195.55	111.33	6.33	3.24	8/47	117.88	12/47
2022	246.4	126.04	5.1	2,1	11/47	80.35	-

Source: estimated by the authors to [5].

In terms of solar energy generation in 2022, Ukraine ranked 11th (5,1 TWh) in Europe. The country became the leader in the growth rate of the solar energy industry in 2019 (+163.96%). And in 2020, Ukraine took the 2nd place (with an indicator of 183.28%), second only to Poland (with an indicator of 275.50%) [5].

Thus, the leading positions in the global solar energy are occupied by the countries of Asia (China, Japan and India) and Europe (primarily Germany). At the end of 2022, less than 1% of the world's volumes of this energy were generated in Ukraine.

Conclusion. Therefore, the modern solar energy industry has already gained high development dynamics. The success story of solar energy compared to other technologies has many reasons, but the key factor is the cost reduction that has made solar energy the world leader in terms of cost reduction. In addition, it is virtually inexhaustible and a free resource. The medium-term forecast for the global economy is difficult to predict. Nevertheless, the world will see high demand for solar energy in the coming years, as this energy is not only economical but also ensures energy security at the national and individual levels. As for Ukraine, it has a significant natural, geographical and investment potential for the renewable energy sources development and therefore it is the main direction in the implementation of state energy saving policy of Ukraine.

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Appendix A

Volumes of energy consumption in the world in the period 1965-2022.

Year	Solar: Consumption		Renewables: Consumption		Primary Energy: Consumption		Share: Solar, %	
	Exajoules (input-equivalent)	Growth rate compared to the previous period, %	Exajoules (input-equivalent)	Growth rate compared to the previous period, %	Exajoules (input-equivalent)	Growth rate compared to the previous period, %	In renewables	In Primary Energy
1965	0	-	0.23	-	155.88	-	0.00	0
1966	0	-	0.26	109.19	164.20	105.34	0.00	0
1967	0	-	0.26	101.11	170.38	103.76	0.00	0
1968	0	-	0.28	109.55	180.69	106.05	0.00	0
1969	0	-	0.30	104.70	192.82	106.71	0.00	0
1970	0	-	0.33	111.05	205.08	106.36	0.00	0
1971	0	-	0.36	108.33	213.45	104.08	0.00	0
1972	0	-	0.38	107.44	224.89	105.36	0.00	0
1973	0	-	0.41	106.10	238.05	105.85	0.00	0
1974	0	-	0.43	105.50	239.50	100.61	0.00	0
1975	0	-	0.43	100.49	240.67	100.49	0.00	0
1976	0	-	0.48	110.71	253.52	105.34	0.00	0
1977	0	-	0.52	108.07	262.84	103.68	0.00	0
1978	0	-	0.56	109.00	273.48	104.05	0.00	0
1979	0	-	0.61	109.31	282.87	103.43	0.00	0
1980	0	-	0.66	107.71	280.56	99.18	0.00	0
1981	0	-	0.69	104.66	279.38	99.58	0.00	0
1982	0	-	0.82	117.83	277.85	99.45	0.00	0
1983	0.00003	-	0.92	113.19	282.35	101.62	0.00	0.0001
1984	0.00007	210.37	1.04	113.18	295.83	104.77	0.01	0.0001
1985	0.00013	186.14	1.11	106.19	303.47	102.58	0.01	0.0001
1986	0.00016	129.25	1.24	112.07	310.26	102.24	0.01	0.0001
1987	0.00011	69.83	1.32	105.87	321.08	103.49	0.01	0.0001
1988	0.00011	96.16	1.36	103.62	333.22	103.78	0.01	0.0001
1989	0.00279	2571.83	1.52	111.34	339.68	101.94	0.18	0.0008
1990	0.00413	148.08	1.71	112.35	343.90	101.24	0.24	0.0012
1991	0.00538	130.11	1.79	104.86	346.37	100.72	0.30	0.0016
1992	0.00497	92.36	1.89	105.59	348.55	100.63	0.26	0.0014
1993	0.00593	119.31	1.97	104.05	351.29	100.79	0.30	0.0017
1994	0.00636	107.24	2.07	105.37	355.77	101.28	0.31	0.0018
1995	0.00680	107.00	2.18	105.09	363.78	102.25	0.31	0.0019
1996	0.00744	109.45	2.21	101.68	374.19	102.86	0.34	0.0020
1997	0.00798	107.20	2.38	107.64	377.99	101.01	0.33	0.0021
1998	0.00864	108.30	2.51	105.25	380.42	100.64	0.34	0.0023
1999	0.00964	111.51	2.66	106.23	387.05	101.74	0.36	0.0025
2000	0.01127	116.99	2.85	107.15	396.88	102.54	0.40	0.0028
2001	0.01505	133.53	2.99	104.93	400.76	100.98	0.50	0.0038
2002	0.01890	125.58	3.41	113.97	409.53	102.19	0.55	0.0046
2003	0.02354	124.55	3.73	109.19	424.09	103.55	0.63	0.0056
2004	0.03083	130.93	4.27	114.55	444.97	104.92	0.72	0.0069
2005	0.04316	140.02	4.83	113.08	459.23	103.21	0.89	0.0094
2006	0.05902	136.74	5.53	114.46	472.29	102.84	1.07	0.0125
2007	0.07958	134.84	6.52	117.95	486.91	103.10	1.22	0.0163
2008	0.12845	161.41	7.78	119.36	492.53	101.15	1.65	0.0261
2009	0.21187	164.95	8.93	114.79	485.02	98.48	2.37	0.0437
2010	0.33884	159.93	10.54	118.02	508.68	104.88	3.22	0.0666
2011	0.65131	192.21	12.14	115.18	520.90	102.40	5.37	0.1250
2012	1.00231	153.89	13.82	113.88	528.18	101.40	7.25	0.1898
2013	1.35989	135.68	15.81	114.39	537.56	101.78	8.60	0.2530
2014	1.91502	140.82	17.63	111.51	543.52	101.11	10.86	0.3523
2015	2.46963	128.96	19.95	113.14	548.14	100.85	12.38	0.4505
2016	3.15704	127.83	22.09	110.75	555.91	101.42	14.29	0.5679
2017	4.26785	135.19	25.36	114.78	566.66	101.93	16.83	0.7532
2018	5.48838	128.60	28.53	112.53	582.38	102.77	19.23	0.9424
2019	6.68013	121.71	31.74	111.22	587.43	100.87	21.05	1.1372
2020	8.00080	119.77	34.80	109.65	564.01	96.01	22.99	1.4186
2021	9.72620	121.57	39.91	114.69	595.15	105.52	24.37	1.6342
2022	12.4137	127.63	45.18	113.20	604.04	101.49	27.48	2.0551

Source: completed and estimated by the authors to [5].